

Life-long learning program
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OIKODOMOS

Consolidation and expansion of a Virtual Campus

WORKPACKAGE 3

CONSOLIDATING AND EXPANDING THE PEDAGOGIC MODEL

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CONTENTS

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	3
2. INTRODUCTION	4
3. COMPENDIUM.....	4
<u>3.1</u> Procedure and process	5
<u>3.1.1</u> Summary	5
<u>3.1.2</u> Description of the working process during the development of the Compendium	5
<u>3.1.3</u> The actual compendium.....	10
4. INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP	11
<u>4.1</u> Set-up of the workshop program.....	11
<u>4.2</u> Workshop Istanbul.....	12
<u>4.2.1</u> Main theme: What is Proximity?	13
<u>4.2.2</u> Integration of the workshop with Learning Activities.....	14
<u>4.2.3</u> Concepts applied to the site	15
<u>4.2.4</u> Related Tasks in Mixed Groups	16
<u>4.2.5</u> Participants at the Workshop / Call for Participation	18
<u>4.2.6</u> Workshop Calendar and Program.....	21
<u>4.2.7</u> After workshop: follow-up	25
<u>4.3</u> Feedback from workshop	27
<u>4.3.1</u> Questionnaire.....	27
<u>4.3.2</u> Results summary	28
<u>4.3.3</u> Direct student feedback.....	29
<u>4.4</u> In conclusion	30
5. WORKPACKAGE CONCLUSIONS.....	30

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This is the report of the activities carried out during the implementation of OIKODOMOS Workpackage 3. This report includes the original formulation of the work package, the activities related to the OIKODOMOS Compendium and the Istanbul Workshop.

2. INTRODUCTION

The chapter includes the workpackage description and the general set-up of the report.

The workpackage description of WP3 in the project work program reads as follows:

Documenting and explaining the OIKODOMOS pedagogic model in order to promote it among the academic and research communities. Facilitating guidelines for the implementation of the model in third party institutions, following the experience gained in the implementation of the learning activities in the previous OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus, including: learning design strategies, technological implementation, evaluation methodology, as well as good practices and suggestions to take advantage of the pedagogic model in different settings (Virtual Design Studio, courses, seminars, blended learning). Consolidation of these aspects and acquired experiences by creating a compendium in digital and printed form including the most relevant content of the previous programme activities: lectures, topics, presentations, selected student works. Implementing the new material in an international workshop with the participating of additional institutions which had been previously acquainted with the pedagogic model through the documentation previously outlined.

The main deliverables of WP3 are 1) a Compendium (deliverable 7); and 2) a Workshop (deliverable 8).

The aim of the Compendium is to give an overview of the pedagogical principles underlying the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus as well as to give a description of the technicalities and hands-on information for any other university to join and start using the OIKODOMOS virtual campus. Evidently, the compendium builds on the experience of the partnership as well as the partnership reflecting on these experiences and developing guidelines and FAQ to help new users of OIKODOMOS. The Compendium is further described in Section 3.

Moreover, the partnership (together with new associate partners) implemented an international workshop. This helped the new partners to understand the dynamics of pre-workshop, workshop and post-workshop learning activities. It improved the experience and understanding of the partnership. The Workshop is described in Section 4

3. COMPENDIUM

The Compendium aimed at:

Publication (digital and printed form), including the most relevant content of the previous programme activities around Joint Workshops: lectures, topics, presentations, selected student works, presented in French, Slovak, and Spanish languages. It will contribute to the enhancement of the pedagogic model and gained experiences to wider academic and non-academic environment. It will also include learning design strategies, technological implementation, evaluation methodology and guidelines for the implementation of the model in third party institutions. It will contribute to the enhancement of the pedagogic model and gained experiences to wider academic and non-academic environment.

Primarily used by students, teachers & professionals in the architecture and urban planning & the general public.

Languages: English, French, Spanish, Italian, Slovak, Turkish

The OIKODOMOS Compendium has been realised by collaboration between partners of OIKODOMOS and includes the main concepts, structures and hands-on information for new users of the virtual campus.

The OIKODOMOS Compendium also includes a wide set of Housing Concepts. These describe important aspects in contemporary housing, include images, concept descriptions and references to additional materials.

The Compendium is available in .pdf in the web portal for wide distribution (www.oikodomos.org/resources/compendium.pdf). OIKOpedia is available at www.oikodomos.org/oikopedia.

3.1 Procedure and process

3.1.1 Summary

The project partners considered that the main goal of the Compendium is to give an introduction to the project to those teachers and researchers interested to join OIKODOMOS. Hence, the OIKODOMOS Compendium needs to be a very useful and easy-to-use document. Not too long but concise and specific. It gives an account of the previously gained experience and transforms that experience into guidelines for implementation in other schools. At the same time, the Compendium gives an incentive to possible new users of the OIKODOMOS learning model and the OIKODOMOS platform.

The Compendium is presented as a complete document in .pdf format, structured in four sections:

SECTION 1 introduces the project, the underlying pedagogic model and its supporting digital platform.
SECTION 2 deals with the implementation of the blended-learning model, in different settings.
SECTION 3 contains the experiences of teachers who have participated in the activities of the virtual campus.
SECTION 4 offers practical information on how to join the virtual campus and contribute to new activities

The document includes links to on-line documents which are collected in the web portal, under the menu RESOURCES. These documents provide in-depth information to those readers that after having a first look to the text decide to know more about the project.

To enable a flexible and layered use of the Compendium (from a first encounter with OIKODOMOS to an in-depth implementation), the Compendium consists in digital (.pdf) form as a reader and has items developed in other digital form (OIKOpedia, presentations, ...). The information is also available through the OIKODOMOS web portal (www.oikodomos.org).

OIKOpedia is the knowledge base which contains the topics studied in the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus in the field of housing studies compiled into a vocabulary. It is structured in concepts that are described in a concise manner, cases of studies associated to the concepts, and references. This collection of concepts provides a valuable learning resource to assist teachers in the design of the learning activities and students in their learning process. As in the Wikipedia, OIKOpedia enables registered teachers to continuously enhance the contents and add new concepts. Content is provided in English as well as in other languages.

When searching for a theme of study in the field of housing to collaborate with other partners, OIKOpedia will be useful.

3.1.2 Description of the working process during the development of the Compendium

October 2010

During the first Skype meeting, the partners developed the idea to include a video explaining how OIKODOMOS can be used in a learning scenario. Also initial ideas for the content of the Compendium were developed.

December 2010 – April 2011

The content of the Compendium was again extensively discussed during the partner meeting in Barcelona on 17th of December 2010. At that time, the Compendium was still seen as a printed in-house publication.

The content should help other learners and teachers to understand the methodology developed during the previous project. The idea at that moment was to have two main blocks of content:

- Case studies of the application of the OIKODOMOS methodology. It should explain the learning sequence –use of blogs, Workspaces and Case Repository–, the pedagogic objectives and results.
- Housing concepts. Each partner should provide 4 or 5 issues which are relevant in contemporary housing (e.g. efficient housing, sustainability, flexibility, ...).

On the basis of this a first table of content for the compendium was produced and made available online for partners to further review through the GoogleDocs. Simultaneously Sint-Lucas provided a template to be used for describing the Housing Concepts. The template was based on the model that La Salle students did use in the learning activity TK2 HOUSING CONCEPTS, posted in the blog and available in the OIKODOMOS Workspaces.

Housing Concepts

SYSTEM	
<p>Housing can never be seen in isolation. It is always part of a larger ensemble: a settlement, a city, the built environment. Considered as an object, a house is always in relationship with other elements: with other houses and buildings, with the surrounding spaces, with the landscape. In order to address housing planning and design, we cannot lose sight of the fact that a house is always part of larger whole of interrelated elements.</p> <p>An organisation of parts within a whole is usually understood as a structure. A system, on the other hand, is a structure with a functional purpose. A structure is a stable organization; a system is a dynamic set of interactions. Adopting a systems thinking approach towards housing conveys not only an understanding of its structural condition but moreover of the functional purpose of the system in which housing is embedded. For instance, we can see housing as part of an ecosystem aimed at reducing energy consumption or as part of an industrialized system whose goal is to produce the maximum number of housing units with minimum cost.</p> <p>The notion of system is equally applicable to living beings, to physical reality and to abstract thinking. In fact, systems thinking blur the separation between these realms, between the natural and the artificial, between the physical and the abstract (von Bertalanffy, 1968).</p> <p>A system is always dynamic, since it is a conceptualization of the interactions between the parts that make the whole, and between these and the environment. Accordingly, a systems thinking approach applied to housing design and planning would pay attention to the dynamic relations between the elements –physical and abstract– which conform housing and other elements of the built environment.</p>	<p>HABRAKEN SUPPORTS</p> <p>In the 1970s, Habraken and the SAH proposed a view of mass housing based on the distinction between two independent systems: support and infill. A support is the collective domain controlled by the community, whereas the infill is the private domain in command of the individual household. By ascribing a specific role in the decision-making process to the individual user – the infill– he or she could participate in the creation of the dwelling.</p>
<p>Van Eyck Orphanage</p> <p>In the 1950s, the architect of the Team X introduced concepts such as individual association, and growth to overcome the notion of functionalism postulated by the modern movement. These ideas were synthesized in the term “net-building”. According to Scharoun, “net-building can be said to epitomize the response character, where the functions come to stretch the fabric and the individual gains new freedoms of action through a new shufled order, based on interconnection, close knit patterns of association and possibilities for growth, distinction and change.”</p>	<p>Habraken's method epitomizes the distinction between building systems and systems building (Ferguson 1975). The former refers to “an assembly of building subsystems and components, and the rules for putting them together in a building” (Ferguson, p. 62). Systems building, on the other hand, has to do with “the application of the systems approach to construction, normally resulting in the organization of programming, planning, design, financing, manufacturing, construction, and evaluation of buildings under single, or highly coordinated, management into an efficient total process” (Ferguson, p. 62). With building systems, for example, it is possible to achieve better management by producing building components in the factory, whereas with systems building, “the architect is not simply incorporating new technology; he is asking society to transform radically its economic organization so as to provide shelter more efficiently” (Ferguson p. 65). Habraken's theory of support and infill, therefore, is an example of systems building applied</p>
<p>L. von Bertalanffy (1968), <i>General System Theory: Foundations, Development, Applications</i>, New York: George Braziller</p> <p>F. Ferguson, <i>Architecture, Cities and the Systems Approach</i>, George Braziller Inc, New York, 1975</p> <p>N. J. Habraken (1972), <i>Supports: An Alternative to Mass Housing</i>, London: Architectural Press.</p> <p>Perbown, A. (2003) <i>How to Recognize and Read Net Building</i>, in Sarkis, S., Allard, P. and Hyde, T. (eds) <i>Case: Le Corbusier's Venice Hospital and the Net Building Hotel</i>, New York: Praeger, pp.91-103.</p>	

Example of the use of the template for the housing concepts

Each partner provided 4-5 themes for the Housing Concepts. Redundancies were checked by Sint-Lucas and the list of Housing Concepts was finalised. All partners were asked to deliver the contents according to the final list and following the template.

Also during this period, La Salle started with the development of the Quick start tutorials.

May 2011

At the consortium meeting in May in Istanbul the status of the work for the Compendium was presented to all partners. The table of contents was reviewed again.

Project partner NEWMINE proposes to make the Compendium as a hands-on document. As an introduction and incentive to the OIKODOMOS project. It should involve and engage people. Therefore a proposal to re-structure the compendium in three parts was discussed and decided on:

- Learning model
- Practical information
- Technical support

The partnership expected this structure to suit the needs of a wide variety of teaching staff, as well as other types of learners (non-professionals, students). The content of the Compendium now included a wide range of contributions varying from the most generic issues (the learning model), to its implementation (practical information) and the use of the platform (technical support). The content of each section anticipated the questions teaching staff might have. The practical information section, for example, contains descriptions of the partners' experience as teachers designing and implementing learning processes.

During the Istanbul meeting, it was also proposed to make the Compendium only in digital form, rather than in printed form as it was originally scheduled. This allowed having the section "Housing concepts" as a wiki accessible in the OIKODOMOS web portal and also makes it much easier to include the latest changes. Adding and editing of content would be restricted to OIKODOMOS partners.

To access these resources, users need to register. This way, possible conflicts with image copyrights were avoided. La Salle searched for available wiki technologies to find out the most appropriate.

The need to translate all contents of the Compendium in different languages was discussed between partners. The initial idea was to have the Compendium translated in the different languages for about 50 pages. The Housing Concepts would stay in English. This position changed during the later development of the Compendium and finally it was judged more useful to have the Compendium only in English and have the Housing Concepts (i.e. the teaching material) translated.

Following on the proposal of making an explanatory video the partnership decided to carry out a web cast to explain the pedagogic model to potentially interested teachers. This webcast took place on the 4th of July using Adobe Connect, and it was hosted by NewMine, one of the associate partners .

An update of the proposed table of contents at this stage was made available in GoogleDocs for partners to discuss:

COMPENDIUM	
Version 10 May 2011	
Table of content:	
Section 01 Learning model	2
What is OIKODOMOS	2
Explaining the learning model	2
Case study implementation	2
Housing concepts:	3
Detail description of the Housing Concepts:.....	3
List of housing concept:.....	3
Description of housing concepts	4
Section 02 Practical information	5
Technological platform	5
Guidelines for implementation:.....	5
Quick start:	6
Tutorials:	6
Protocol:	6
Technical support.....	6

The 'case study implementation' in this table refers to interviews with project partners (teaching staff) accounting their experience with OIKODOMOS. Three interviews were conducted. It was also considered that Technical Support would be a part of the section on Practical Information.

July – September 2011

As this new table of contents was discussed again, a new gap was detected: there was no information on the previous activities (Workspaces and Joint Workshops). Hence, a new chapter was added to describe the four OIKODOMOS workshops carried out so far.

Concerning the format of the Compendium two possibilities were discussed:

- 1) The first one was to reduce each chapter in both Sections to a short abstract and then provide a link to the materials posted in the web portal.
- 2) The second option was to provide more elaborated texts for Section 1 and short descriptions for Section 2 which will be complemented by links to web-based materials.

The second option was chosen and the web-based materials were produced by La Salle.¹

1. The pedagogic model: *learning structure*

The pedagogic model underlying the learning environment OIKODOMOS Workspaces is based on this structure:

```

graph TD
    LW[Learning Workspace] --- LA1[Learning Activity]
    LW --- LA2[Learning Activity]
    LW --- LA3[Learning Activity]
    LA1 --- LT1[Learning Tasks]
    LA1 --- LT2[Learning Tasks]
    LA2 --- LT3[Learning Tasks]
    LA2 --- LT4[Learning Tasks]
    LA3 --- LT5[Learning Tasks]
    LA3 --- LT6[Learning Tasks]
  
```

A Learning Activity is a well-defined stage in the process of learning, for instance, "Site analysis", "Analysis of precedents",

TIPS : TIPS: TIPS: TIPS: TIPS : TIPS: TIPS : TIPS : TIPS : TIPS

- To begin the learning design in OIKODOMOS Workspaces, teachers from different schools need to agree on a theme which they want to develop (e.g. "Lifelong dwelling") during a certain period of time (a week, a month, a semester, ...) – not necessarily coincident with the academic timetable.

-> you can use the Forum in www.oikodomos.org to propose themes, exchange ideas and get in contact with other teachers

- Once a group of teachers have agreed to work on a common topic, one of them can open a Workspace.

-> you need first to be a registered user to access Workspaces. A login can be obtained at support@oikodomos.org

TIPS : TIPS: TIPS: TIPS: TIPS : TIPS: TIPS : TIPS : TIPS : TIPS

On-line introductions to OIKODOMOS pedagogic model. Source: ARC Ingeniería i Arquitectura La Salle

Finally, the Housing Concepts needed to be improved on. Each concept was reviewed several times. Then, the Housing Concepts were sent for proof reading. After the proof reading the contents were introduced by each partner in the OIKOpedia. Once the proof-read concepts were introduced in OIKOpedia, partners translated the concepts in their local languages.

A first draft of the Compendium was sent to all partners by mid September 2011 for commenting. Partners evaluated the draft and made suggestions about adjusting, redirecting content and format.

¹ See www.oikodomos.org/resources

Compendium
Version: 09 September 2011

Section 01 The OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus.
01 /// What is OIKODOMOS
02 /// The OIKODOMOS Learning and Teaching Model
03 /// Implementation of the pedagogic model: the Joint Workshops
04 /// Case study implementation
Interview with Angel Martin Cojo:
Interview with Baril Ozmen Mayer:
Interview with Kris Scheerlinck:
05 /// OIKOpedia. Housing concepts:
List of housing concepts:
Description of housing concepts

*
-
Section 02 Supporting documentation.
01 /// Technological platform, Introduction
02 /// Participants Forum
03 /// Guidelines for implementation
04 /// OIKODOMOS Tutorials

Compendium Table of Content 9th of September 2011

October 2011

During this period, the Compendium was fine-tuned.

NewMine checked the content of the Compendium in terms of usability and readability. They suggested to reduce the amount of text and to add screenshots to accompany URL links.

Compendium
|

About the Compendium..... 4
Section 01 -The OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus 5
 CH01 /// What is OIKODOMOS?..... 6
 CH02 /// The OIKODOMOS Learning and Teaching Model 8
 XX// Aligned Learning and Teaching 8
 XX//Learning Outcomes..... **Error! Bookmark not defined.**
 XX//Blended learning: reconceptualising the relationship between teaching and learning..... 10
 CH03 /// Technological platform 12
 01 /// Workspaces 12
 02 /// Case Repository 13
Section 02 –Implementation of the pedagogic model..... 14
 CH01 /// Learning design with OIKODOMOS Workspaces 16
 CH02 /// Integrating online activities and joint workshops..... 17
 CH02 /// Joint workshop: Housing and Proximity 21
 Set-up of the workshop program **Error! Bookmark not defined.**
 Workshop Istanbul 23
 Main theme: What is Proximity? (see comment at beginning of section) 21
 Integration of the workshop with Learning Activities 24
 Concepts applied to the site 26
 Related Tasks in Mixed Groups 26
 Participants at the Workshop / Call for Participation 22
 Workshop Calendar and Program **Error! Bookmark not defined.**
Section 03 -The experience of learning and teaching in the Virtual Campus 29
 CH01 /// What teachers say about their experience in the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus? 31
 Some interviews..... 31
 CH02 /// Recommendations for future learning activities 37
Section 03 – Joining the virtual campus: supporting materials and information 39
 CH01 /// Starting up 41
 CH02 /// OIKOpedia: Housing concepts 41

Compendium Table of Content end of October 2011

3.1.3 The actual compendium

The Compendium consists out of four sections:

- SECTION 1 introduces the project, the underlying pedagogic model and its supporting digital platform.
- SECTION 2 deals with the implementation of the blended-learning model, in different settings.
- SECTION 3 contains the experiences of teachers who have participated in the activities of the virtual campus.
- SECTION 4 offers practical information on how to join the virtual campus and contribute to new activities

The Compendium is available on the menu RESOURCES at the OIKODOMOS web portal² and the housing concepts are available at OIKOpedia³.

OIKODOMOS A virtual campus to promote the study of dwelling in contemporary Europe

Lifelong Learning Programme - Erasmus Virtual Campus - Reference: 134370-LLP-1-2007-1-ES-ERASMUS-EVC
Erasmus Accompanying Measures- Reference: 177090-LLP-1-2010-1-ES-ERASMUS-EAM

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Education and Training

Home Project Partners **Resources** Activities Reports References Publications Newsletters Media News About *Admin

Supporting materials for participant institutions

OIKODOMOS Compendium. It provides an overview of the project which helps teachers to get introduced to the pedagogic methodology of the virtual campus, with examples of its application.

What is Oikodomos? An audiovisual (5 min.) introducing the project development, objectives and outcomes. Also available in Youtube: <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sK5bBMtqDWA>

OIKODOMOS pedagogic model. A narrated presentation introducing the OIKODOMOS pedagogic model.

Learning design with OIKODOMOS Workspaces. The purpose of this document is to introduce the pedagogic model of OIKODOMOS to teachers in order to help them designing new learning activities and participating in the on-going ones.

OIKODOMOS Workspaces in 5 Steps: an application case. This document summarizes the process of designing and implementing learning activities followed in the Workspace "Proximity".

OIKOpedia is the knowledge base of the OIKODOMOS project. It contains the topics and concepts studied in the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus.

OIKODOMOS Housing Concepts is a compilation of the content of the first edition of the OIKOpedia.

Integrating the OIKODOMOS Case Repository in the curriculum. A report of the process followed at BTU Cottbus to integrate the OIKODOMOS Case Repository in one of their teaching modules.

External evaluation of learning activities in OIKODOMOS Workspaces. A report of the external evaluation of the works of the Workspace "Proximity" carried out by a group of teachers from ETS Arquitectura Valencia.

Participate

OIKODOMOS 2011-2012: If you are a teacher interested to participate in the OIKODOMOS activities, this COMPENDIUM will help you to get introduced to the methods and tools for learning design in this virtual campus.

Platform

A technological platform has been specifically developed and implemented for the Oikodomos Virtual Campus to support a blended-learning pedagogic model. It consists of two environments: Workspaces and Case Repository.

OIKODOMOS WORKSPACE

This environment supports project-based learning activities, such as the development of a project -architectural and/or urban- in a collaborative manner. It facilitates the collaboration among distant learners, carrying joint learning activities in different settings, physical and virtual: design studios, seminars and courses.

OIKODOMOS CASE REPOSITORY

This is a digital repository of housing case studies, which is constructed collaboratively by

OIKODOMOS web portal, menu RESOURCES. Source: ARC Ingeniería i Arquitectura La Salle

² www.oikodomos.org/resources/compendium.pdf

³ www.oikodomos.org/oikopedia

OIKOpedia Login

English ▼

Concept

- Customization
- Flexibility and Variability
- Gated Communities
- Housing Amenities and Utilities
- Impact of ICT on the Human Psyche
- Mix of Urban Functions
- Mixed-Use Housing
- Neighborhood
- Participatory Process
- Pattern
- Proximity
- Reconversion and Regeneration
- Social Diversity and Availability
- Social Mix
- Suburban Housing
- System
- Universal Design

Customization

[Introduced by Leandro Madrazo , 2011-11-25 13:31:26]

Customisation derives from 'to customize' or 'to build, fit, or alter according to individual specifications'. It could also have the meaning 'to personalize' or 'to make personal or individual' and 'individualize' or 'to adapt to the needs or special circumstances of an individual'.

Therefore, to customize a house means to design and build a place to live according to the specific needs or demands of those who will occupy it, or to alter an existing place to meet such needs or demands.

To design and build customised dwellings in collective housing, it is necessary to apply the term 'mass customisation', which is the opposite of 'mass production'. To mass-produce a house means to build the same model many times in order for it to be useful to many people.

However, to 'mass customize' a house it is necessary to manufacture many components that can be combined in various ways. The combination of these components could be calculated and visualised with a computer program, and the results could be spread through interconnected computer networks. Thus each individual or the members of a family, with the help of an architect, can choose the house in which they want to live, according to their requirements and within a collective environment.

On the other hand, a 'mass-produced' dwelling, which is part of collective housing, could also be adaptable or flexible so that it can be altered and therefore 'customised'. The spaces of this dwelling may be indeterminate, without a prescribed hierarchy; they can have many uses or might change physically, long term or short term, with walls that can be located in different places, with special furniture or with moving partitions.

Related Cases

Support and Infill: Flexibility

Through the Living Homes website, people can choose, within certain limitations, among several houses, designed by Kappe, Kieran, Timberlake; and can customize them by adding rooms and choosing materials and finishes. A flexible house may be part of a support. Following the theory of John Habraken, a support is a permanent structure, framework or infrastructure containing secondary structures, separate units of housing or in-fill built with industrial components, which are interchangeable.

Customization of half-finished houses in Chile, designed by Elemental

Unfinished or expandable houses are buildings designed by architects but whose inhabitants conclude the process, meaning they continue to build their homes. In this case the architects can design cores or half-finished houses, planting the seed and leaving certain guidelines. Thus a dwelling is not a finished product but is part of a process.

www.oikodomos.org © ARC Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle-Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona, 2007-2011

OIKOpedia homepage. Source: ARC Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle

The Compendium has been provided in digital form only. To facilitate the upgrading of the content, we have considered more appropriate to distribute it through the web portal in .pdf format. The content of the .pdf document is complemented with a series of separate presentations available at the web portal, menu RESOURCES. Considering that English is the required language to share the learning activities, we have divided the content of the compendium in two parts: a methodological content (.pdf and on-line presentations, only in English), and housing topics available through OIKOpedia in multiple languages (English, French, Italian, Spanish, Slovak, and Turkish).

Hence, the OIKODOMOS Compendium might become a continuously changing document, incorporating the most recent experiences.

4. INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP

4.1 Set-up of the workshop program

This OIKODOMOS Joint Workshop provided an opportunity for institutions and students to participate in the design and implementation of the learning activities carried out in the Virtual Campus. Three Workshops have already taken place at the Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Sint-Lucas Ghent (October 2008), Institut d'Urbanisme de Grenoble, Université Pierre Mendès-France, Grenoble, France (April 2009) and the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava (October 2009). The fourth international OIKODOMOS Workshop has taken place in the Istanbul Technical University (ITU), in May 2011.. Dr. Beril Ozmen, from EMU, was the responsible for the site coordination and local organization of this last workshop, together with Dr. Kris Scheerlinck and Tomas Ooms from Sint Lucas School of Architecture.

Istanbul, the site for the OIKODOMOS workshop, (HERA- archive)

The workshops within the OIKODOMOS project must be seen in the wider context of the learning activities carried out collaboratively in the virtual campus rather than as separate activities. They are part of sequences of learning activities which start before the workshop and continue after it.

OIKODOMOS A virtual campus to promote the study of dwelling in contemporary Europe
www.oikodomos.org

Lifelong Learning Programme - Erasmus Virtual Campus - Reference: 134370-LP-1-2007-1-ES-ERASMUS-EVC
Erasmus Accompanying Measure - Reference: 17700-LP-1-2010-1-ES-ERASMUS-EMF

OIKODOMOS is a Virtual Campus co-financed by the Long LRM Learning Programme of the European Union to support housing studies in Europe. In the first two years of the project, 2007-2009, OIKODOMOS has developed, implemented, tested and evaluated an innovative pedagogic model based on a blended learning approach which combines on-line learning activities carried out in web-based environments - specifically designed for this Virtual Campus - with seminars, design studios and workshops physically taking place at the participating universities. The goal of the third year project activities (2010-2011), is to consolidate the pedagogic model and expand the Virtual Campus to other institutions.

This OIKODOMOS Workshop provides an opportunity for institutions and students to participate in the design and implementation of the learning activities carried out in the Virtual Campus. Three Workshops have already taken place at the Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Sint-Lucas Ghent (October 2008), Institut d'Urbanisme de Grenoble, Université Pierre Mendès-France, Grenoble, France (April 2009) and the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava (October 2009). The fourth international OIKODOMOS Workshop will take place in the Istanbul Technical University (ITU), in May 2011. The workshop is organized by the HREC Housing Research and Education Center in ITU with the cooperation of the HERA Center from the Eastern Mediterranean University.

4th International OIKODOMOS WORKSHOP: HOUSING and PROXIMITY
Istanbul Technical University, 2-6 May 2011

Photography: HERA/Active

The main objective of this International Workshop will be to analyze - or rethink - the status and design of the contemporary housing in densification processes taking place in European suburban landscapes. Besides, existing theories and practices of the compact city - as a way to preserve the natural landscape, control and limit the urban sprawl, reduce energy consume and consolidate social cohesion, reality often shows a contrasting practice of low dense landscapes conditioning an efficient and sustainable functioning of urban systems. This dual reality of the built environment -compact cities vs. low density suburban areas- will be equally considered during the workshop. This workshop focuses on the relation between the housing typology and its suburban surrounding and stimulates critical reflection about recent phenomena in an international context. The workshop will start from the idea that urban space is based on models of proximity on a small scale, as well as on a bigger scale. Therefore, we should start asking ourselves: **what does proximity refer to?**

Important dates:
March 31, 2011 - Deadline for sending CV, motivation and statement
April 15, 2011 - Reviewers feedback and notifications of acceptance
May 2, 2011 - Start workshop

Education and Culture DG

Housing and Proximity

Proxemic models affect our reading and use of space and refer to an important cultural dimension of the built environment: systems of intimate, personal, social or public distances are based on our education and cultural references. However, proximity can refer as well to the built environment itself, or to the general urban patterns.

Manuel de Solà Morales once stated that urban space can be seen as "a system of relative distances": systems of distances between housing blocks, between individual dwellings, between leisure facilities and residential neighborhoods, between industrial areas, wastelands and residential development areas. As if they were sets of rules to be decided, coded and decoded at various levels, by various agents. These systems of distances do not operate exclusively on a bigger scale; they penetrate the very domain of the dwelling itself: distances from the street to the front door, from the entrance door to the living room, the distance between the kitchen, or the heart of the dwelling, and the bedrooms, being the more intimate territories within the domestic space. Dwellings could be seen as configurations of distances, where physical distances obtain additional meaning: bigger or smaller distances can mean higher or lower possibility of contact, of sharing space. In other words, proximity also refers to a social dimension: sets of distances define the level of collective use within a project, from the scale of the domicile, to the scale of the neighborhood. Distance can become social distance.

In recent years, social distance is increasingly understood as a buffer, a safety measure: distance has become a device to guarantee separation and segregation. In this context, the following question arises: how territorial mechanisms which prioritize individual identity replace mechanisms based on collective strategies to share space?

Call for participation

Participation in the OIKODOMOS Workshop is open to all interested architecture and urban planning students. To be eligible, interested students should send the following documents which will be evaluated by an evaluation board:

1. a brief letter of motivation (max 500 words in an A4 page)
2. a CV, including samples of design projects or design research related to housing (max 4 pages size A4)
3. a statement about the proposed topic of the workshop, "Proximity" (a text of max 500 words, in an A4 page, including optionally one image)

All information (in English) should be submitted as a single pdf document to oikodomos@architectuur.sintlucas.wenk.be

Selected participants will receive notification of acceptance by April 15th, 2011 and will not have to pay a registration fee. After attending all activities they will receive a certificate of participation.

Members of the evaluation board are:

Viera Jeklova, Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava, SLOVAKIA
Leandro Madrazo, Escuela Técnica Superior d'Arquitectura La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona, SPAIN
Angel Martin Cojo, Escuela Técnica Superior d'Arquitectura La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona, SPAIN
Thomas Ooms, Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Department Architectuur Sint-Lucas, Brussels/Ghent, BELGIUM
Beril Ozmen Mayer, Eastern Mediterranean University, NORTH CYPRUS
Hifsiye Pulhan, Eastern Mediterranean University, NORTH CYPRUS
Paul Riddy, University of Southampton, UNITED KINGDOM
Kris Scheffelinck, Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Department Architectuur Sint-Lucas, Brussels/Ghent, BELGIUM/
Escuela Técnica Superior d'Arquitectura La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona, SPAIN
Stefano Tardini, Università della Svizzera Italiana, Lugano, SWITZERLAND
Jan Tazuy, Institut d'Urbanisme I.U.U., Université Pierre Mendès, Grenoble, FRANCE
Johan Verbeke, Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Department Architectuur Sint-Lucas, Brussels/Ghent, BELGIUM

More information about:

- the workshop activities, please access www.project-oikodomos.blogspot.com
- the workshop organization, please contact us at oikodomos@architectuur.sintlucas.wenk.be
- the OIKODOMOS project, please contact us at project@oikodomos.org

Leaflet of the program of the Istanbul workshop

4.2 Workshop Istanbul

The Istanbul international OIKODOMOS Workshop has taken place in the Istanbul Technical University (ITU), in the first week of May 2011. The workshop was co-organized by the local institution HERA: Housing Education Research Advisory Center, from the Eastern Mediterranean University. The set up was supported as well by the HREC: Housing Research and Education Center

in Istanbul Technical University. The partners joining this academic activity with teachers and students were:

- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava, Slovakia
- Escola Tècnica Superior d'Arquitectura La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona, Spain
- Eastern Mediterranean University, Famagusta, North Cyprus
- Institut d'Urbanisme IUG, Université Pierre Mendès-France, Grenoble, France
- Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Department Architectuur Sint-Lucas, Brussels/Ghent, Belgium
- External participants (teachers and students) from Gebze Institute of Technology, Faculty of Architecture Cayirova, Gebze/Kocaeli, Turkey

The main objective of this International Workshop was to analyze -or rethink- the status and design of contemporary housing in densification processes taking place in European suburban landscapes. Urban development strategies, as well as architectural interventions, were discussed and proposed during the workshop.

Next to existing theories and practices of the compact city -as a way to preserve the natural landscape, control and limit the urban sprawl, reduce energy consume and consolidate social cohesion, reality often shows a contrasting practice of low dense landscapes, conditioning an efficient and sustainable functioning of urban systems. This dual reality of the built environment –compact cities vs. low density suburban areas- was addressed in the workshop.

Both high and low density settlements can be considered spatial constructions which embody one and the same spatial dimension, which we can name –tentatively– “Proximity”.

4.2.1 Main theme: What is Proximity?

The theme of the workshop –Proximity– was described in the following terms:

Proxemic models affect our reading and use of space and refer to an important cultural dimension of the built environment: systems of intimate, personal, social or public distances are based on our education and cultural constraints. Therefore, proximity embraces multiple dimensions (personal, social) and at various scales (domestic, urban): proximity encompasses both the perception of space by inhabitants and the planning of space by professionals.

Manuel de Solà-Morales once stated that urban space can be seen as “a system of relative distances”: systems of distances between housing blocks, between individual dwellings, between leisure facilities and residential neighbourhoods, between industrial areas, wastelands and residential development areas. As if they were sets of rules to be decided, coded and decoded at various levels, by various agents. These systems of distances do not operate exclusively on a bigger scale: they penetrate the very domain of the dwelling itself: distances from the street to the front door, from the entrance door to the living room, the distance between the kitchen, as the heart of the dwelling, and the bedrooms, being the more intimate territories within the domestic space. Dwellings could be seen

as configurations of distances, where physical distances obtain additional meaning: bigger or smaller distances can mean higher or lower possibility of contact, of sharing space. In other words, proximity also refers to a social dimension: sets of distances define the level of collective use within a project, from the scale of the domicile, to the scale of the neighbourhood. Distance can become social distance.

In recent years, social distance is increasingly understood as a buffer, a safety measure: distance has become a device to guarantee separation and segregation. In this context, the following question arises: have territorial mechanisms which prioritize individual identity replaced mechanisms based on strategies to share space?

Text provided by Kris Scheerlinck

4.2.2 Integration of the workshop with Learning Activities

The Workshop was part of the learning activities carried out within the learning workspace “Proximity”. Learning Activities are a structural component of the OIKODOMOS pedagogic model. Each learning activity is composed of a sequence of tasks that are carried out by groups of students from the participating institutions in the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus. The objectives of the tasks can be to comment a housing concept, to map a site coherently, to define an urban strategy, to design an architectural intervention or to evaluate previous outcomes to build on. Therefore, the activities that were carried out in the workshop are part of a larger sequence of activities that started before and continued after the workshop in the Virtual Campus.

These are the learning activities of the workspace Proximity which encompass the work done before, during and after the Istanbul workshop:

LA21: Defining Proximity

[understanding the different notions of the concept]

In this Learning Activity, the questions were: what does proximity mean when reading or designing housing projects? What are the constituting parameters defining proximity? What is the theoretical and conceptual framework of proximity?

LA22: Exploring Proximities: Housing & Urban Context

[analysis of existing urban environments at different locations, from the point of view of “proximity”]

Different models of proximity can be used to read a site and propose some coherent interventions. Here, various strategies were compared and discussed.

LA 27: Implementing Proximities: Social Context

[participatory actions, collaboration between professionals and citizens]

Proximity is related to social dimensions, inherent to the built environment and its organization: from the domestic scale till the scale of the neighbourhood, social concerns were studied and discussed.

LA 24: Designing Proximities: Architectural Strategies

[interventions involving transformations of buildings and urban environments]

Architectural interventions or transformations define in a very precise way how people, activities or buildings relate physically, visually and socially: this learning activity focused on the architectural implications of proximity.

LA25: Discussing Proximities

A critical reflection of all previous Learning Activities allowed the use of the outcomes in later projects and provided a coherent reading of the contemporary housing landscape.

The work done during the Joint Workshop was integrated in the sequence of tasks carried out within these Learning Activities, before, during and after the workshop. This way, the preparatory work done in the Virtual Campus served as starting point of the Workshop, and the results of it fed the activities done afterwards.

Workspace "Proximity". Structure of the learning activities. Source: ARC Ingeniería i Arquitectura La Salle

4.2.3 Concepts applied to the site

The knowledge acquired in the activities carried out by participants before the workshop were applied to a case of study in the area of Istanbul.

The selected study area for the workshop activities was the Göksu Quarter in the Anatolian (Asian) side of the metropolis, at a further distance from the city and at the footprint of the second bridge (Fatih Bridge), which connect the two continents.

The area is situated around a stream, Göksu, which flows to the Bosphorus and an adjacent green park which was a famous recreation area in Ottoman times. On the other side of this stream, there is a typical sea-side village with vernacular examples. There is castle called 'Anadolu Hisari' that relates to the riverside and to the Bosphorus. This area was once a clearly suburban area; but now it has been absorbed by Metropolitan Istanbul. On the hilly sides, with the sea as a horizon of the district, new development can be observed, based on less qualitative architectural strategies.

The area is problematic at this very moment but its potentials allow interesting interventions to upgrade its sustainable potential.

The Göksu – Anadolu Hisari site, North Istanbul, Turkey

4.2.4 Related Tasks in Mixed Groups

Apart from the integrated “local” Learning Activities and Tasks, three specific tasks were defined, to be developed before and during the workshop in mixed groups (each group represents minimum 3 partner institutions: the same groups will be used during the workshop):

1. Task 16: Proximity: Extracting Themes, LA 25 Discussing Proximity

The main goal of this common task was to reflect on the results of the preparatory Learning Activities related to the Proximity Workspace, done at each institution during the last semester. This common reflection exercise served as an introduction to the Workshop Activities in Istanbul.

During the last months, many related tasks were defined and fulfilled at the participating institutions: some of them were developed on a theoretical or a conceptual level, others related to a specific site, its potentials, problems and/or a specific housing program. During the following discussion or evaluation sessions, some recurring themes seemed to appear, sustaining an interesting discussion among students and professors. Themes like collective spaces, barriers, transition spaces, clusters, social cohesion were repetitively referred to while commenting the outcomes of the different tasks. In this task, these recurring core themes were used to introduce and accelerate the workshop activities and assure the continuation of the learning process: the idea was to use these common themes to cross-check the outcomes of the previous Learning Activities and further build on them. This task was developed by mixed groups before the workshop in Istanbul.

During the introductory session (Istanbul, Monday May 2), 10 groups of participants presented the so-far outcomes of the previous tasks, “filtered” by the theme that is assigned to each group. These were the themes, assigned to the 10 groups:

- group 1: distances and connectivity
- group 2: collective spaces
- group 3: discontinuity and barriers
- group 4: social cohesion
- group 5: housing clusters
- group 6: sets of relative distances
- group 7: accessibility and permeability
- group 8: domestic and urban sequences
- group 9: transitions
- group 10: intermittent spaces

This cross-institutional set-up was organised in such a way as to provide coherence and consistency in Learning Activities and an interesting starting point for the planned workshop activities.

2. Task 17: In Situ Göksu Quarter: Signs of Proximity, LA22: Exploring Proximities: Housing & Urban Context.

The main goal of this task was to apply the concept of proximity to the site in a short timeframe: each group made a photographic reportage of the visited site, using the concept of proximity as the main focus. This task, developed during the second day of the workshop, helped to introduce and read the site, as well as to speed up the workshop activities. This way, an immediate forum of discussion was celebrated within and in between the mixed groups of participants.

The outcomes of this task allowed home base participants, as well as external participants, to be accurately introduced to the site, to stimulate interaction with the workshop activities.

During the visit to the site, all participants looked for “signs of proximity”: where and how can we read models or patterns of proximity? How can we use photography to represent these signs of proximity? This task was developed by each mixed group: during the visit to the site on Tuesday morning (see calendar), all participants made a photographic reportage of the Göksu Quarter. After the visit and arriving at the ITU campus studio, each group selected 10 photographs that represent models or cases of proximity on the site.

Results of photographic mapping in by group 5

3. Task 18: Mapping Proximity: Göksu Quarter, LA22: Exploring Proximities: Housing & Urban Context.

This (mixed) group task tried to explore and disentangle the present mechanisms of growth and use of the selected site and propose some possible transformation by adding housing program.

Using the concept of proximity, all participants read and mapped the site and its direct environment and proposed a sustainable housing project. Developing this task during the workshop week, and based on the visit and all provided information, the following questions were raised:

- Can we frame the historical growth of the site, taking into account as well cultural and social factors?
- What accessibility does the site have? On which model of mobility do the inhabitants/visitors rely?
- Which are the morphological characteristics of the site? What does the figure/ground scheme look like?

- Which functions are located on the site and by whom and when are they used?
- Which type of barriers can be detected on different levels and where do they manifest themselves?
- Can we detect conflicts of use(rs)? Are there any underused or unused spaces?
- Which set of (relative)distances can be recognized on different scales?
- Do we recognize patterns of social cohesion on the site?
- What is the level of compactness of the site? Where do we recognize low dense and high dense conditions?
- What is the structure of the site? How does the existing housing program relate to its environment?
- Related to all previous questions and taking into account a given addition of housing program, which solutions/transformations do we propose?

Mapping Proximity, work by group 3

4.2.5 Participants at the Workshop / Call for Participation

The partnership called for participation in the workshop where a group of international students in architecture, urban planning and urban design worked together around the general topic of Housing and Proximity. All interested students sent the following documents to be eligible for selection by the International Scientific Committee (23 applications received):

1. a brief cv, with full name, postal addresses and e-mail addresses, mentioning type, scale and contents of academic projects of design or research (max 500 words)
2. a brief motivation letter (max 250 words)
3. a statement about the proposed general topic of the workshop (a text of max 250 words, with one image included)

17 students were finally selected by the international scientific committee:

- Viera Joklova, Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Bratislava, Slovakia
- Leandro Madrazo, Escola Tècnica Superior d'Arquitectura La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona, Spain
- Angel Martin Cojo, Escola Tècnica Superior d'Arquitectura La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona, Spain
- Hifsiye Pulhan, Eastern Mediterranean University, North Cyprus, Turkey
- Tomas Ooms, Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Department Architectuur Sint-Lucas, Brussels/Ghent, Belgium
- Beril Ozmen Mayer, Eastern Mediterranean University, North Cyprus, Turkey
- Paul Riddy, University of Southampton, United Kingdom
- Kris Scheerlinck, Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Department Architectuur Sint-Lucas, Brussels/Ghent, Belgium/ Escola Tècnica Superior d'Arquitectura La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona, Spain
- Stefano Tardini, Università della Svizzera Italiana, Lugano, Switzerland
- Jan Tucny, Institut d'Urbanisme IUG, Université Pierre Mendès-France, Grenoble, France
- Johan Verbeke, Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Department Architectuur Sint-Lucas, Brussels/Ghent, Belgium

External participants (after call, external partners): total 17 students (23 applications)

These selected participants were complemented by some invited local students of some of the Project Partners:

Partner participants: total 28 students

LaSalle: 5 students
Sint-Lucas: 5 students
FASTU: 6 students
EMU: 8 students
IUG: 4 students

Total 45 student participants which were organized in 10 teams of 4/5 students

The participating teachers were teachers from the project partners, as well as from the host institution and from the associate partner institutions: total 15 teachers

LaSalle: 2 teachers
Sint-Lucas: 2 teachers
FASTU: 3 teachers
EMU: 3 teachers
IUG: 2 teachers
ITU: 2 teachers
Gebze: 1 teacher

Groups of Participants OIKODOMOS Workshop "Proximity", Istanbul Technical University, 2-6 May 2011			
First name	Last name	Institution	Country
group 1: distances and connectivity			
Usua	Aseginolaza	La Salle	Spain
Bedia	Tekbiyik	EMU	North Cyprus
Maxime	Mongodin	IUG-UPMF	France
Jakub	Kolarovic	FASTU	Slovak Republic
Torkan	Borna	ITU *master st	Iran
group 2: collective spaces			
Eduardo	Arriola	La Salle	Spain
Michal	Janak	Sint-Lucas	Slovak Republic
Yusuf Özerdem		EMU	Cyprus
Marie	Daix	IUG-UPMF	France
Deniz Uluksar		Gebze Institute of Technology	Turkey
group 3: discontinuity and barriers			
Sheila	Femiza	La Salle	Spain
Klaas	Dhaene	Sint-Lucas	Belgium
Barbara	Borscova	FASTU	Slovak Republic
Dilara Eksi		Gebze Institute of Technology	Turkey
Gül Sibel		ITU	Turkey
group 4: social cohesion			
Alejandro	Tramulles	La Salle	Spain
Madalina	Cheregi	Sint-Lucas	Romania
Samira	Darbandsari	EMU	Iran
Thaibaud	Boularand	IUG-UPMF	France
Duygu Özer		Gebze Institute of Technology	Turkey
group 5: housing clusters			
Robert	Torralba	La Salle	Spain
Adam	Fabo	FASTU	Slovak Republic
Saloumeh	Khayyat	EMU	Iran
Philippine	Waterkeyn	IUG-UPMF	France
Juan	González Alonso	ETSA Valladolid / Sint Lucas	Spain
group 6: sets of relative distances			
Hulda	Sigmarsdottir	Sint-Lucas	Iceland
Fatemeh	Ghafari	EMU	Iran
Hatice	Sadikoglu	ITU - PhD student	Turkey
Seçil Kona		Gebze Institute of Technology	Turkey
Jeroen	Stevens	Sint-Lucas	Belgium
group 7: accessibility and permeability			
Peter	Loffler	FASTU	Slovak Republic
Mahsa	Salimi	EMU	Iran
Zumra	Okursoy	ITU - Senior urban plan+arch	
Marina Petit Terradas		URL LaSalle / WENK Sint Lucas	Spain
group 8: domestic and urban sequences			
Martin	Truba	FASTU	Slovak Republic
Sara	Davarpanah	EMU	Iran
Ezgi	Hazar	ITU *master st	Turkey
Martina Radeva		University of Sofia / WENK Sint Lucas	Bulgaria
group 9: transitions			
Aminreza	Iranmanesh	EMU	Iran
Mahsa	Safae	ITU *master st	Iran
Esra Öner		Gebze Institute of Technology	Turkey
Tim Van Verdegem		WENK Sint-Lucas	Belgium
group 10: intermittent spaces			
Guillaume	Dopchie	Sint-Lucas	Belgium
Anna	Soosova	FASTU	Slovak Republic
Aref	Arfaie	EMU	Iran
Ezgi	Bay	ITU *master st	Turkey
Adil	Çamur	ITU	Turkey

4.2.6 Workshop Calendar and Program

Day one: Monday May 2nd, 2011

Many participants arrived on Sunday night in Istanbul, others on Monday morning. This timeframe, some extra hours before the official start of the workshop, provided some margin to present participants to each other and to discuss or finish the first presentations programmed the first day.

In the afternoon, Prof. Dr. Orhan Hacıhasanoğlu, Dean of the Faculty of Architecture, ITU, welcomed all students and teachers to the university.

HREC Vice-Director, Prof. Dr. Ahsen Özsoy, Vice Rector, ITU, provided some information about the goals and history of the HREC and welcomed all participants.

HERA-C Director, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Turkan Ulusu Uraz, EMU, representing the organizing institution, welcomed all guests and presented an overview of some ongoing projects.

OIKODOMOS coordinator, Prof. Dr. Leandro Madrazo, introduced the project, its pedagogic model and objectives.

Prof. Dr. Kris Scheerlinck, representing WENK Sint Lucas as leading partner institution for this workshop, introduced the concept of Proximity and referred to the already developed tasks that introduced the workshop.

After this series of more general introductions by the hosting and organizing institutions, the students participated by a presentation of the results of the Learning Activities before the workshop. During this introductory session, 10 groups, of participants (mixed so each groups represents at least 3 different partner institutions) presented the so-far outcomes of the previous tasks, as part of the Proximity Workspace. The idea was that the partner participants explained the set-up and results of the “local” preparatory assignments, extracting the core themes, recurring concepts in the previous tasks/discussions. Each group focused on a specific theme (to avoid overlap).

After a short Tea / Coffee Break, Prof. Dr. Gülsün Sağlamer gave a general introduction about Istanbul, pointing out historical and more recent phenomena of urban transformation: “Istanbul: Uncertainties and Transformations”

After this lecture, Prof. Dr. Yurdanur Dulgeroğlu Yuksel introduced “Housing Typologies in the Process of Change” which focused more on the importance of the variety of housing typologies within the Metropolis of Istanbul.

Later, Prof. Dr. Beril Özmen presented a short introduction to the Göksu Quarter site, to prepare for the excursion planned for the second day.

In the corridor of the University building where all activities were having place, a small event was organized by all partner institutions: a small exhibition was set up to present the provisional outcomes of the ongoing Learning Activities: each partner prepared some panels that represented the set-up and results of the previous tasks (intro studied site in Gent, Brussels, Bratislava, Barcelona, North Cyprus...) The aim was to inform outsiders of the ongoing OIKODOMOS Learning Activities.

Example of the panels of the exhibition organized in the corridors of the university campus in Istanbul

Day two: Tuesday May 3rd, 2011

The second day of the workshop started with a boat trip on the Bosphorus, towards the Göksu site. A 45 minute boat trip introduced students and teachers to the wider region of Istanbul and its treatment of periphery, where the studied site was situated. While on the boat, some extra information was provided for all participants related to the history and transformation of the riverfront area.

Arriving on the site, all participants were invited to work on the photographic mapping of the site (Task 17: In Situ Göksu Quarter: Signs of Proximity) while a guided tour was organized for all participants. The second part of the visit was used for individual exploration of the site and gather information.

After arriving again at the university in the early afternoon, students started working in the mixed groups and focused on the selection and editing of the selected photographs. As well, some first impressions were discussed with the teachers about the urban context of the site.

Later that afternoon, a lecture was organized with the title “Tale of the City on Water”: Dr. Fatma Erkök explained the morphogenesis of the site and focused on the importance of water features for the growth and transformation of the site on different levels.

Day three: Wednesday May 4th, 2011

The third day of the workshop started in the morning with a small informal presentation by all groups of the selected photographs of the “Signs of Proximity” task: all teachers joined group discussions to evaluate those first proposals and to stimulate further development of the next task. From that moment on, all groups started working on Mapping Proximity: Göksu Quarter, LA22: Exploring Proximities: Housing & Urban Context (Task 18).

These group dynamics with alternating peer review continued during the afternoon session.

BARRIERS
A barrier is a structure which blocks or impedes something. wikipedia

TYPES: Physical, Visual, Physiological, Personal, Sound,...

SCALE: Houses, City, Country,...

NATURAL <-> BUILT

different INTENTIONS

DISCONTINUITY
1. A distinct break in continuity or sequence in time.
2. A sharp difference of characteristics between parts of something. wikipedia

1. Caused by a stop >> BARRIERS
2. Caused by a change of environment

Relation to PROXIMITY

More BARRIERS; less PROXIMITY
More DISCONTINUITY; less PROXIMITY

A barrier:
longer time to destination
less orientation
less union with destination
>>> Less Proximity

Different barriers. Relation house and environment

physical and visual barrier

visual connection with front door

surface change

OIKODOMOS // GROUP 3 // BARRIERS AND DISCONTINUITY // May 2nd, 2011
Barbara Borscova , Dilara Eksi, Sheila Ferniza, Gul Sibel Gedik, Klaas Dhaene

warmth, sound and physical barrier but with visual proximity

Discontinuity in space: SANAA's Rolex center

Urban Discontinuity: High-rise differences

Street

Gated community

Proximity in the street

No proximity in the gated community

Discussing Proximity, student work by group 3

Day four: Thursday May 5th, 2011

In the fourth day of the workshop the participants focused on putting together all previously obtained data, reviewing the different proposals and making a synthesis to prepare for the final presentation. The outcomes of previous Learning Activities were used to complement the “local” project. The complexity of the subjects discussed during that day was notably higher than in previous sessions.

At the end of the day, different scenarios were discussed to prepare the final presentation planned for the last day; this was discussed with all present teachers in the afternoon session.

Day five: Friday May 6th, 2011

The last day of the workshop started with the final presentation by the mixed groups: each team had 15 minutes to present their project and reflection on proximity, applied to the Göksu site in Istanbul.

All groups tried to make a synthesis of previously obtained outcomes in the pre-workshop Learning Activities and the information and proposals that were related to the Istanbul site. In a way Göksu site was used to present, discuss and propose housing projects, taking the concept of proximity as a guideline. After each presentation, all teachers gave feedback and evaluated briefly the presentations.

Part of the final presentation by group 1

After all presentations, some general conclusions were drawn after which the certificates of participation were handed over to all students. All participants were informed about the planned follow-up activities.

The event was concluded by a short tour in the school building and a tea party on the rooftop of the ITU campus building.

4.2.7 After workshop: follow-up

The follow-up of workshop contents, seen as a continuation of the Learning Activities followed two parallel courses:

1. The mixed groups continued working on the proposals, reviewing concepts and presentation matters and presented by mid June their final proposals, all communicated through the workspace Proximity. The teachers suggested the groups to “specialize” in the area, defined by the theme assigned to each group during the workshop (e.g. an architectural or urban project, based on housing clusters, transitions...). Task 19 was defined to describe this task that focused on the continuation of “Discussing Proximities”.

Task 19: Göksu Quarter Revisited, LA25: Discussing Proximities.

The outcomes of the previous task were most interesting and proved a critical and coherent attitude related to the site and its potentials. However, the short available time for presentation and the format of this did not always allow framing the urban proposals. The following questions, aiming at a broader reflection about proximity, remained:

- How can we relate the proposals at different levels to the concept of proximity, what is the (social) model behind the proposed interventions?
- Can we define the proposal as a unique strategy or were reference projects used? If yes, how were they used?
- How can we relate the proposals to a broader discourse on low or high dense landscapes and its possible (re)densification? Did we base our interventions on tactics of densification or did we only reconfigure the existing urban fabric and do we know why?
- When did we use systematic approaches? When a structural approach? (see feedback and evaluations)
- What is the vision behind the proposal and which strategies can be used to implement them?

This post-workshop task of Revisiting the proposed Urban Projects provided some distance of the work done and tried to frame the proposals. A coherent and critical description of the proposal was elaborated by each mixed group with the following objectives:

- frame the proposed intervention conceptually (see remaining questions above)
- describe the proposal in a way external students or teachers could understand the proposal

2. The local groups (per partner) continued working on their ongoing Learning Activities and related tasks and further built on the (provisional) outcomes of the workshop: for example, the students in Brussels used the presentations of the workshop to further develop their architectural proposals in Linden. The first studio session, once back at the home faculty, started with a series of presentations about the so-far obtained results, to inform the students who did not participate in the Istanbul workshop to be able to build on these results.

Presentation of the workshop results at the Sint Lucas campus in Brussels

3. Some **external review** was done of the previous outcomes of the Learning Activities, realized before or during the Istanbul Workshop. In this case, teachers from ETS Arquitectura de Valencia, Spain and from the Gebze Institute of Technology, Turkey, started a discussion and evaluation of the different proposals and studies as they were presented by the students of the workshop, or even the previous Learning Activities, like the studio “Empowering Suburbia: Mapping Proximity in Linden”, by the students of the Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, Department Architectuur Sint-Lucas, Brussels/Ghent, Belgium. This extra feedback allowed the students and participants to continue and deepen the discussion about the main topic, housing and proximity, as part of the Proximity virtual workspace.

OIKODOMOS: WORKSPACES Proximity

Home Calendar **Participants** Groups Learning Activities Tasks Sequences Resources Galleries Tutorial

TK1 Understanding of Proximity / Deliverable 28 February 2011

Deliverable Description

Profile: Lucio, Alberto

Comments

Michael, Leandro on [16/02/2011]
The image of Magritte suggests more the feeling of separation than closeness. Closeness is represented in terms of being "next to" -one figure next to the other, one window next to the other- but the composition conveys a extreme feeling of isolation and separation at the same time: isolation of one person to the other, one scene in its own bubble, in "half" terms), extreme detachment between people and houses (the figures do not inhabit the built environment, they live in another space, some from another world).

Rubina, Martina on [21/02/2011]
I really like the parallel between Magritte's drawing and the concept of suburbia - a sea of individuals, each wanting to be independent and separate, and succeeding on its own, local scale. But when you observe this phenomenon on a big scale, you have a surreal, national experience. You can't help but ask yourself, what are they doing there?

Luis, Peter on [27/02/2011]
I like the separation from the picture. Those persons seems pretty unaware of each other and they mind their own business. No link between them. Although they can be close to each other in space, they seem to have no relationship in social scale.
I think you have explained reliability and scale of proximity really well. Examples helped a lot in understanding. Maybe more pictures would help even more. Did I start really understand last paragraph. Do you consider described things as best?

Evaluations

S									
LO1	The student will be able to discuss the most relevant urban concepts and their design.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
LO2	The student will be able to define the issues affecting the actual design of residential architecture (following the new social structures, globalisation, materials...)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						

The painting of Magritte and the perception towards suburbia, Linden are interpreted in a sensitive way of comprehension. Also the best of the work is very to the point, and coherent with the semantic meaning of "proximity".

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4.3 Feedback from workshop

At the end of the workshop, a quality evaluation was carried out by Mr. Paul Riddy, from Viveka Consulting.

4.3.1 Questionnaire

Part of the evaluation of the workshop employed a student-focussed questionnaire, based and designed to evaluate how student-centred the approach was and if there were any issues or strengths which could be reviewed or disseminated respectively. The questionnaire had a similar format to the one used during the previous OIKODOMOS workshops and was distributed to 45 students at the end of the final session. A total of 42 students responded, and 90% of these scored all of the questions.

The full set of questions, along with more detailed evaluation is available in the OIKODOMOS WP7 evaluation report. A summary of the overall data, including the number of comments associated with each question, is included in table below. In analysing the data the comments have been grouped into sub-topics.

Q. No	Questions	Mode	Median	Total No. of comments
	Pre Joint Workshop evaluation questions			
11	Before going to the Joint Workshop I was clear about the purpose of the international cooperation in our (school) learning activities	2	2	1
12	The Learning Activities created by teachers in the Workspace were relevant, appropriate and clear.	2	2	6
13	From the start of these activities I was given full descriptions of the learning activity, including learning objectives/outcomes	2	2	1
14	The learning activities in my school before going to the Joint Workshop were well integrated with the learning activities during the Joint Workshop	2	2	3
15	I used this Workshop Workspace regularly before the workshop to gain the information about the site.	2	2	3
16	<i>Tools used</i>	Not relevant to this discussion		
17	Using these tools I was able to access enough information to prepare for the work in Bratislava	2	2	0
18	Electronic/computer communication helped me to get to know the participants from the other schools well enough to help collaboration before going to the Joint Workshop	2	2	6
19	The academic support at my University was sufficient for preparation of the learning activities to be carried out in the Joint Workshop	2	2	2
20	The processes to get technical and academic support were adequate	2	2	1
21	The response times to questions from learners by staff were adequate	2	2	2
22	I discussed information on the Joint Workshop site with other students and teachers in advance of the workshop	2	2	6
23	I found students contributions to the discussions helpful	2	2	3
24	I found professors contributions to the discussions helpful	1	2	5
25	Working online collaboratively with students from other countries has been a good experience	1	1	7
	Joint Workshop Evaluation			
26	I was clear about the purpose/objective of the Joint Workshop when I arrived	2	2	2
27	The Introduction / briefing sessions made clear all aspects of the Joint Workshops	2	2	2
28	I was clear about the competences or learning outcomes to be gained from completing the workshop before arriving	2	2	0
29	I am clear about the way in which my work during the workshop will be assessed	2	2	3

30	The taught sessions were relevant and appropriate	2	2	5
31	The taught sessions were clearly presented	2	2	3
32	I thought the taught sessions were well integrated with the workshop theme	2	2	1
33	I thought the taught sessions fitted well with the work in groups	2	2	1
34	There was adequate access to computing resources	2	2	8
35	I had enough time to do the work	2	2.5	2
36	I had enough time not working / free time	4	4	5
	I understand what work I have to do in my institution which follows on from this joint workshop	2	2	2
38	I was able to communicate effectively with the members of my group	2	2	5
39	What was your most important or interesting learning?	N/A	N/A	51
40	What did you like, what is done well?	N/A	N/A	46
41	What could be done differently?	N/A	N/A	54
42	Any other comments	N/A	N/A	18
	Total no. of comments			254

Istanbul Joint Workshop Evaluation Questionnaire results, June 2011. Data scaled : 1-4, Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly disagree, + Don't know & Not Applicable as N/A.

4.3.2 Results summary

All questions except two have mode and median values which are the same, indicating limited spread of the scores. The majority of scores are the same and equal 2, with three values differing, discussed further below. This contrasts strongly with the post Bratislava workshop questionnaire, in which 75% of questions had mode value of 1, the remainder 2. The former questionnaire was web based, delivered electronically post workshop, and the students were from a smaller group of institutions who had participated in the project for 2 years.

The number of student comments, associated with each of the questions is also listed. Apart from questions 39-42, which asked only for comments, the number of comments is small. These questions were meant to capture information about the students overall experience but most of the responses refer to Joint Workshop activities or are ambiguous. Except for the responses to 39-42, the majority of the comments refer to single points which are different, indicating a diversity of opinion from which statistically meaningful conclusions cannot be drawn. This is illustrated in the discussion about three specific questions below, a summary of responses being given after each question.

Q. No	Questions	Mode	Median	Total No. of comments
24	I found professors contributions to the discussions helpful	1	2	5
	This refers to contributions before the joint workshop and the comments gave a mixed response: 2 positive, 1 more needed, 2 poor English was a problem. The difference in median and mode indicates there was a spread of opinions and there was also a difference in the spread of responses between institutions.			
25	Working online collaboratively with students from other countries has been a good experience	1	1	7
	6 of 7 responses indicated this was good and important experience, on that it wasn't and face-to-face work was better.			
36	I had enough time not working / free time	4	4	5
	The responses all indicated that there was not enough time and 2 specifically mentioned the lack of time to visit the city.			

Questions with Mode<>2, all refer to during the Joint Workshop

The ambivalence of students experience of the Joint Workshop and associated activities indicated in the questionnaire scores may be misleading. Some indication of what students thought about the Joint Workshop experience may be better indicated through comments posted to the questions below.

Q. No	Questions	Total No. of comments
39	What was your most important or interesting learning?	51
	16% appreciated the learning which came from cultural differences 29% found the experiencing the differences between individual and national approaches to architecture valuable 22% found working in groups a valuable experience	
40	What did you like, what is done well?	46
	41% appreciated the interactions through working in groups 22% found the teaching tasks and presentations useful 13% found the organisation good/very good	
41	What could be done differently?	54
	9% wanted less lectures and more time to visit 22% wanted more time /free time 22% would have liked different organisation of the groups and more opportunity for whole group interaction	
42	Any other comments	18
	50% found the Joint Workshop a very good experience.	

Open comment only questions (no scores)

The questionnaire results indicate that the students found the overall learning experience valuable and for some students, the learning which came from working in a cultural diverse group has been highlighted as being valuable. Many of the comments point out small things which could be done to improve the learning experience. Taking these into account, from a student centred point of view areas to review are:

Consistency across institutions in:

- Clarifying role of the Learning Activities and their Learning Outcomes (or objectives / competences) to the students
- Design of learning activities to engage all students in these and the associated communication in advance of the workshop

During the workshops:

- Ensuring potential equability of the experiences of individuals in groups (e.g. ensuring language ability in advance of workshop).
- Structuring the work to allow free time to explore the city and culture of where the event is held.

4.3.3. Direct student feedback

Next to the questionnaire, some of the students were asked to make a short video, explaining personally their experiences from the workshop. The contents of these interviews were used to evaluate the organization and results between the partners. Some example follows, interview by Klaas Dhaene, recorded in June 2011.

“Hello, I’m Klaas Dhaene and participated the Oikodomos workshop in Istanbul from May 2nd until May 6th. I m a student of Sint-Lucas Brussels in Belgium and studying my first master of Architecture. I will first describe the experiences of the workshop and after the important things I specifically learned.

The short time of the workshop in Istanbul was used very efficiently since everybody prepared in advance with his team a short presentation about proximity. This speeded up the process of familiarization with the topic and with the team itself.

The trip to the Göksu site was well organized in advance and the fact we took a boat to the other side of the river instead of a bus, was fascinating, since we could discover the outstretched metropolitan area of Istanbul directly. The specific task we had to complete this day forced us to look in a different way to the given site: we had to make a photo-reportage about "signs of proximity".

The lectures, which meant to support the workshop, speeded up the process and were generally interesting and showed us the problems and needs of the city and the site.

I learned to look in a different way to urban problems, influenced by the topic of proximity. This new vision for me will influence my future carrier, even if I would not want to be influenced. There is no way to switch this 'proximity' off!

The experience to work together with other people of a different nationality, culture and habits, was most interesting. It wasn't always easy to come up with a collective on-site-strategy in such a short notice but it was worth it. If those discussions would have been held while in my home country, everybody would had the same opinion about these topics, now it was more dynamic and enriching. This diversity made the workshop a very interesting five days experience!"

4.4 In conclusion

The integration of the Learning Activities, planned and conducted at the different partner institutions on different European sites during the academic year, with the workshop activities has been an interesting and successful challenge on an academic level. A common general theme, a shared timing for all participating students and teachers, together with coordinated steering of contents, evaluation criteria and feedback, has allowed the participating partners to construct an efficient learning platform. During the academic year, multiple parallel discussions at different scales have contributed to an enrichment of the discourse about contemporary housing in Europe, creating thus an open and flexible space for reflection and research. The workshop outcomes have been of an international high level. Moreover, the workshop and related Learning Activities open up new perspectives for the further development of a **virtual campus to promote the study of dwelling in contemporary Europe, OIKODOMOS**.

5. WORKPACKAGE CONCLUSIONS

This work package 'Consolidating and expanding the pedagogic model' was composed of two different kinds of activities:

1. Building on the experience from the first OIKODOMOS project, the partnership has been able to create the OIKODOMOS compendium. This is a useful guide for new or associate partners to understand the dynamics of OIKODOMOS and to understand the practical implications of joining the virtual campus.
2. The organisation of a workshop, and the related learning activities, have contributed to deepen in the understanding of the OIKODOMOS pedagogic methodology and to expand the virtual campus.

Both of these activities have been successfully realised by the partnership and the outcome are at the disposal to the academic community which might be willing to continue enhancing the OIKODOMOS virtual campus.